

Deliverable 6.4

Dissemination and Communication Strategy and Periodic Dissemination and Communication Report (Interim Report 2)

Work Package 6

SAH

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Executive summary

This deliverable contains the 2nd interim report on dissemination and communication, as well as an update of the dissemination and communication strategy of Watson that was outlined in “D6.2 - Dissemination and Communication Strategy and Periodic Dissemination and Communication Report (Interim Report 1)”. It describes the activities that have been carried out until Month 18 under “Work Package 6 - Ecosystem Building and Exploitation” and presents an overview of the changes being made to the plan to ensure that Watson effectively reaches its key target groups.

As the project reached its second year, the emphasis progressively shifted from the creation of relevant channels and content to the inclusion of the initial results and findings from ongoing research on Watson, and the intensification of dissemination efforts at both physical and online events.

During the reporting period, significant progress was made in establishing Watson’s brand and communicating its objectives. A robust digital presence was developed, with the project’s website attracting 3,104 unique visitors and over 10,000 page views. Complementing this, Watson’s social media strategy proved effective, particularly on LinkedIn, where the project reached 1,584 followers and achieved over 62,000 impressions. Watson also produced three newsletters and gained visibility in various media outlets, including radio programmes and food magazines. Additionally, the project organised 6 workshops and participated in 53 events across Europe. As a result, Watson has engaged with over 90,000 stakeholders through its communication channels. Moreover, the project’s contributions to 10 international conferences have significantly enhanced its visibility.

As the project moves forward, the strategy will continue to evolve with a stronger focus on targeted stakeholder engagement. Efforts will be intensified on social media, particularly LinkedIn, while the website will undergo further optimisation to maintain high levels of engagement. Additionally, the project will create new dissemination materials, such as mini-series episodes; continue to strengthen synergies with related projects and organise more workshops and training activities. Lastly, Watson will significantly increase the number of peer-reviewed papers and articles published in leading scientific journals and conference proceedings, while contributing to other types of publications to reach a broader audience beyond academia. In parallel, the project will develop high-level materials tailored for policymakers, including the publication of white papers and sets of best practices, accompanied by relevant statistics from various EU and associated countries.

Key words: Dissemination, communication, ecosystem building, stakeholder engagement

Project summary

Watson is a 3-year project that has been funded by the EU's research and innovation framework programme, Horizon Europe, to combat fraudulent practices in the food supply chain. Watson's interdisciplinary consortium of 47 partners (40 Beneficiaries, 2 Affiliated Entities and 5 Associated Partners) across 20 countries will develop a holistic traceability framework that will integrate data-driven services, intelligence-based toolsets and risk-estimation approaches, enabling food safety authorities to identify and prevent fraudulent activities.

The project aims to improve the sustainability of food chains by reducing food fraud. This will be achieved through systemic innovations that (a) increase transparency in food supply chains through improved track-and-trace mechanisms containing accurate, time-relevant and untampered information for the food product throughout its whole journey, (b) equip authorities and policy makers with data, knowledge and insights in order to have the complete situational awareness of the food chain and (c) raise the consumer awareness on food safety and value, leading to the adoption of healthier lifestyles (mid-term) and the development of sustainable (and greener) food ecosystems.

Watson will develop a digital technology reference architecture integrating novel technologies such as AI-supported early warning system for food safety authorities based on the processing of various data with connection to food fraud related database; Resilient Data driven and IoT-based Services for Improved Tracing and Tracking; Fast, Inexpensive and Flexible Tools for Authenticity Control, Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) and Data Analytics, which enable transparency within supply chains through the development of a rigorous, traceability regime, and novel tools for rapid, non-invasive, on the spot analysis of food products. The proposed framework is tested and demonstrated in 6 use cases across different European countries considering different operational procedures and diverse environments:

1. Tackling counterfeiting of wine in Portugal.
2. Rapid traceability of extra virgin olive oil in Italy.
3. Improved traceability of high-value products in cereal and dairy chains in Finland.
4. Preserving the authenticity of PGI honey in Spain.
5. Identification of possible manipulations at all stages of the meat chain in Germany.
6. Combating of fish counterfeiting in Norway.

Watson aspires to improve sustainability of food chains by increasing food safety and reducing food fraud through systemic innovations that increase transparency in food supply chains by improved track-and-trace mechanisms, equip food safety authorities and policy makers with data, knowledge and tools, and raise consumers' awareness on food safety and value.

Abbreviations

APR	Soc. Agricola Organizzazione Di Produttori Aprol Umbria Soc. Cooperativa
ASI	Asociación De Investigación Industrias De La Carne Del Principado De Asturias
BAU	Universitat Bayreuth
BIO	Biocos IKE
BWE	Bulgarian Winemaking & Export Association
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
CER	Center For Research & Technology
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche
DBC	DBC Europe
DEC	Associação Portuguesa Para A Defesa Do Consumidor
EIT	European Institute Of Innovation & Technology
ESP	Espersen A/S
EU	European Union
EUF	European Food Information Resource
EUN	Euronews Eun
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
FIB	Research Institute of Organic Agriculture
FSH	Foodscale Hub
HAI	Hämeen Ammatti Instituutti
HER	Hermes AS
HUB	Humboldt-Universität Zu Berlin
IFA	Iseki Food Association
IGP	Asociación Para La Promoción Y Gestión Igp Miel De Asturias
INE	Instituto De Engenharia De Sistemas E Computadores, Tecnologia E Ciência
INR	Institut National De Recherche Pour L'agriculture, L'alimentation Et L'environnement
INT	Netcompany - Intrasoft
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Result

KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LGL	Bavarian Health And Food Safety Authority
LIC	The Lisbon Council For Economic Competitiveness And Social Renewal ASBL
MET	Metro Anonymi Emporiki Kai Viomichaniki Etaireia Eidon Diatrofis Kai
MIG	Migros Ticaret Anonim Sirketi
MIT	Mitera GMBH
MRI	Max Rubner-Institut, Federal Research Institute Of Nutrition & Food
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NTU	National Technical University Of Athens
PDA	Consejería De Medio Rural Y Cohesión Territorial Del Principado De Asturias
REG	Resilience Guard Gmbh
RFF	Reframe.Food
SAH	Smart Agro Hub
SIN	Sintef Nord As
SYN	Synelixis Solutions S.A.
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UBI	Ubitech Limited
UCD	University College Dublin
UNC	Unione Nazionale Consumatori
UPC	UPC Konsultointi OY
UVMB	University Of Veterinary Medicine Budapest
VTT	Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus
WCS	Wellics LTD
WDP	World Development Programme
WHO	World Health Organization
ZPS	Zveza Potrošnikov Slovenije Društvo

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1. Introduction

This document builds upon and expands on the Watson project's deliverable "D6.2 Dissemination and Communication Strategy and Periodic Dissemination and Communication Report (Interim Report 1)", which was delivered in M4 and initially established the dissemination and communication strategy project. The activities defined and reported in this deliverable are part of the "Work Package 6 - Ecosystem Building and Exploitation", thus involving tasks "T6.1 - Dissemination, Communication and Watson Branding" and "T6.2 - Stakeholders' Training, Community Engagement and Liaison with Other Initiatives".

In general, Watson dissemination and communication strategy remains pertinent. Its primary objective is to establish a well-structured plan that ensures the broad promotion of the project's use case studies, developed concepts, technologies and the potential for future implementation. Thus, collaboration between Watson partners is essential to keep ensuring that the project results are widely disseminated to the relevant audiences.

1.1 Structure of the document

This document has been meticulously structured based on the guidelines and recommendations set forth by the European Commission regarding the communication and dissemination of Horizon Europe projects. These guidelines serve as a framework to ensure effective and impactful communication strategies throughout the project's lifecycle. By following these suggestions, the document aims to establish a comprehensive and well-organised approach to Watson communication and dissemination activities.

Thus, it incorporates key elements and best practices outlined by the European Commission to maximise the project's visibility, engagement and knowledge-sharing. The structured framework allows for a systematic and coherent presentation of the project's communication and dissemination plan, ensuring that all relevant aspects, such as target audiences, key messages, communication channels and evaluation methods are thoroughly addressed. Additionally, adhering to the European Commission's recommendations facilitates alignment with the broader goals and objectives of the Horizon Europe programme, ensuring that the project's communication and dissemination efforts are in line with the overarching framework of the programme and its desired outcomes.

More precisely, the document is structured into 8 main chapters:

- **Chapter 1** and **Chapter 2** include introductory information about the project, its objectives, target audiences and visibility rules of EU funding.
- **Chapter 3** provides a detailed description of Watson communication and dissemination plan.

- **Chapter 4** and **Chapter 5** describe the communication and dissemination strategy that is being implemented.
- **Chapter 6** offers an overview of the communication and dissemination tools, as well as reporting on the activities carried out and providing some key figures.
- **Chapter 7** presents the monitoring and performance assessment of the communication and dissemination activities throughout the project's lifetime.
- Finally, **Chapter 8** includes the concluding remarks of the deliverable.

2. Update of Watson communication and dissemination strategy

In this section, we will provide an update on the Watson communication and dissemination strategy, reflecting on the lessons learned during the first half of the project (M1-M18). Overall, the strategy outlined in D6.2 remains relevant and continues to guide our efforts. The initial phase, "Phase 1" (M1-M12), focused on building an audience and raising awareness about the project in its first year, has been completed. The project has now moved into "Phase 2" (M12-M30), where the primary goal is to keep stakeholders informed about the scientific and technological advancements of Watson. This phase emphasises communicating how the project's outcomes meet the needs of different stakeholders and fostering meaningful engagement to build a community around Watson. These dissemination activities are expected to intensify after Month 18, coinciding with the release of several deliverables on the solutions being developed.

Subsequently, "Phase 3" (M30-M36) will focus on setting the stage for the future exploitation, commercialisation and sustainability of Watson's innovations. This phase will involve intensifying efforts to share the project's results, further engaging with the Watson community, and capitalising on the existing momentum to secure additional partnerships and investments. Promotional activities will also play a crucial role in sharing the project's successful experiences, which can serve as models that can be replicated in other contexts or projects, enabling others to benefit from the knowledge and experience gained through the project.

2.1 Project objectives

Drawing upon a wealth of internationally recognised expertise and leveraging the latest advancements in technology, five primary objectives were proposed that align with the project's aspirations. Three of these five primary objectives are closely related to communication and dissemination activities. For this reason, Table 1 outlines these three primary objectives, and which communication and dissemination Key

Performance Indicators (KPIs) will be used to measure them. In addition, the full list of KPIs for Watson’s dissemination and communication activities is included in Table 9.

Table 1: Watson objectives and related communication and dissemination KPIs

Project objectives	Communication and dissemination KPIs
Obj2 – Validate and demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed Watson methodological framework and toolset through 6 validation campaigns in 6 different subsectors of the European food system that will pave the way for rapid uptake of the proposed framework and its systemic solutions, with the active engagement of several food chain stakeholders.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No. of stakeholders registered for the demonstration events >5,000 - Number of training workshops for consumers and food safety authorities >3
Obj4 – Ensure wide communication and scientific dissemination of the innovative Watson results to the research, academic, and international community, raising awareness and promoting multi-stakeholder cooperation and information sharing in order to tackle fraudulent activities in the food chain.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of mini-series episodes on food traceability, food product authenticity and sustainable diets >3 - Number of (online and physical) training activities in schools, neighbours and open farm days >15 - Liaison with relevant EU funded projects >15 - Number of stakeholders from the food industry comprising the valorisation board of the project >50 - Number of new stakeholders engaged through the project’s communication channels >50,000 - Number of participants in the Open Farm Days and other training activities >2,000
Obj5 – Mainstream project results towards relevant policy making organisations and standardisation bodies in order to foster science-enabled policy reforms related to traceability and authenticity in food systems aiming to increase the global competitiveness of the European food sector.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Best practices, regulations and lessons learnt, material from >20 countries - Number of white papers for policy recommendations >3

2.2 Communication and dissemination purpose, means and phases

The strategy for communication and dissemination of project outcomes will adhere to principles and best practices that have been successfully tested by consortium partners in previous projects. This strategy encompasses several key components:

- Precise identification of the target audience for the knowledge generated and the creation of tailored dissemination materials that align with their specific requirements.
- Specification of communication methods and channels to effectively engage with the intended audience.
- Preparation of both electronic and printed materials to facilitate wide-reaching dissemination.
- Development of a well-structured timeline to ensure the most efficient dissemination of project findings and outcomes.

Moreover, the main objectives of this strategy are as follows:

- a) Define a clear and distinctive brand identity for Watson that will be consistent online and offline, and it will represent the cornerstone values of the project.
- b) Ensure broad visibility of Watson’s work and disseminate its results to its target stakeholder groups to effectively promote Watson’s offer and gain wider acceptance.
- c) Facilitate the exploitation of Watson results for partners, jointly and individually, and for the overall research communities, by promoting the development of innovative Watson-based solutions for the effective generation of socio-economic impact.
- d) Ensure broad visibility and promotion of Watson, beyond the programme’s borders, via strategic and operational coordination of specific communities through dedicated efforts involving all stakeholders.
- e) Support the sustainability of Watson beyond its lifetime.

The key objectives of the dissemination effort involve overseeing the knowledge gained during the project and sustaining continuous connections with essential stakeholders, encompassing the wider public audience, research community and regulatory bodies. This approach is geared towards promoting additional research initiatives and discovering fresh market prospects.

Recognising and understanding the distinctions between these components is essential for the effective implementation of communication and dissemination activities. For this reason, Watson follows the guidelines provided by Horizon Europe and the Watson Grant Agreement, as described in Table 2.

Table 2: Purposes and means of communication and dissemination activities

	Communication	Dissemination
Purpose	The purpose of communication in projects is to inform and engage multiple audiences, including society, and to showcase the benefits of research and innovation.	Dissemination focuses on making project results available to audiences who may use them, aiming to enable the utilisation and adoption of all publishable outcomes.
Means	This is achieved through various means, such as maintaining a project website, sending newsletters, issuing press releases, creating videos and conducting interviews, distributing project factsheets and brochures, and utilising social media platforms.	This is accomplished through methods, such as scientific publications, policy briefs, workshops, and demonstrations, as well as sharing results on online repositories that encompass research data, software and reports.

Watson’s communication and dissemination plan emphasises the importance of public information, community building and engagement. The plan recognises that increasing the effectiveness of the public information strategy requires careful consideration of key activities and dependencies.

Finally, Watson's communication and dissemination strategy is structured in three phases (Figure 1):

- a) **Phase 1 (M1-M12)**: engagement of stakeholders from the food chain, consumer associations and scientific communities.
- b) **Phase 2 (M12-M30)**: promotion through communication and dissemination activities of Watson's initial findings and results.
- c) **Phase 3 (M30-M36)**: uptake of the solutions and preparation of exploitation plans for Watson's further deployment.

Figure 1: Watson communication and dissemination phases

2.3 Target groups

This communication and dissemination plan takes into consideration the needs and interests of different target groups to establish clear communication and dissemination goals for each subgroup. By understanding the characteristics and preferences of these audiences, the plan aims to employ the most effective communication and dissemination channels and methods to reach them.

The deliverable “D6.2 - Dissemination and Communication Strategy and Periodic Dissemination and Communication Report (Interim Report 1)” delivered in M4 started by identifying the primary target groups, which are the main audience segments that the project engages with. These target groups include researchers, academia, policymakers/funders, industry stakeholders, or other relevant stakeholders identified in the project. D6.2 also identifies secondary target groups, which are additional audiences that may indirectly benefit from or contribute to the project's objectives, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Watson target groups

Watson target groups
Association of Consumers
Farmers
Food Products Transportation Companies
Food Producers
Retailers
Food Processors
Nutritionists
Food Safety and Certification Authorities
Researchers in the agrifood and technology sectors
Industrial communities representing the food industry
Policymakers and regulators in agrifood sectors
Members of EIT Food, FAO, WDP other relevant associations
Non-European agencies or institutions and initiatives such as FAO, OECD, WFP, IFAD, SDG

To effectively communicate with these target groups, D6.2 also identified the key offerings and messages of the project. This involves highlighting the unique value propositions, outcomes, and benefits that the project provides to each target group. By understanding the specific interests and needs of these groups, it ensures that the messages and offerings are tailored to resonate with their priorities and motivations.

Building on D6.2, this D 6.4, “Dissemination and Communication Strategy and Periodic Dissemination and Communication Report (Interim Report 2)” determines the most appropriate means to reach each target group. This involves a combination of communication and dissemination channels, such as websites, social media platforms, newsletters, presentations, press releases, workshops, conferences, or peer-reviewed journals. By selecting the most relevant and impactful communication and dissemination channels, D6.4 shows how the project has already begun to maximise the reach and engagement of its messages within each target group. Overall, both deliverables D6.2 and D6.4 establish a targeted and strategic approach to communication and dissemination by aligning the project's goals, messages, and offerings with the specific needs and interests of different target groups. This ensures that the project's outcomes and impact are effectively communicated and understood by the intended audiences, facilitating meaningful engagement and collaboration throughout the project's lifecycle.

2.3.1 Stakeholders’ engagement

In order to maximise the scientific and socio-economic impact of the project, Watson has undertaken a thorough analysis of the needs and priorities of its diverse stakeholders. This analysis serves as the basis for defining and implementing a set of actions aimed at effectively promoting the project's outcomes. The

objective is to identify the most suitable approaches for reaching, interacting with, and communicating with each group of relevant stakeholders. To achieve this, the project is engaging in the following activities:

- (a) **In-depth stakeholder analysis:** Watson conducts a comprehensive analysis to understand the specific needs and priorities of different stakeholder groups. This analysis provides insights into the most effective modalities of engagement and communication for each group.
- (b) **Establishment and management of liaisons and synergies:** Watson actively collaborates and build relationships with relevant initiatives at both national and pan-European levels. This includes leveraging existing communities and fostering synergies to enhance the project's impact.
- (c) **Participation in events:** Watson actively participates in relevant events and organises its own events. These events provide opportunities for knowledge sharing, networking and showcasing the project's outcomes.
- (d) **Stakeholder engagement, community building and capacity building:** Watson prioritises stakeholder engagement by actively involving them in project activities. The project also focuses on community building efforts to foster collaboration and knowledge exchange. Additionally, Watson supports capacity building initiatives to enhance the skills and capabilities of the stakeholder community.

Figure 2: Watson's activities for stakeholder engagement

As the project progresses, more details and specific actions will be added to the plan. This iterative approach ensures that the strategy remains dynamic and adaptable to the evolving needs of the stakeholders. The overall aim is to grow the size, reach and activities of the multidisciplinary user community, leading to increased scientific and socio-economic impact of the project. This task is built on the strong existing networks of Watson partners. This is achieved by pursuing the concrete activities shown in Figure 2.

In addition, within Watson’s framework, there is a dedicated task (T6.2) to establish strong collaborations and partnerships with various stakeholders in the field. This task specifically focuses on engaging with other EU-funded initiatives and projects that share similar objectives or have complementary targets. One notable example is the projects funded under the HORIZON-CL6-2022-FARM2FORK-01-04 topic, which aims to develop innovative solutions for preventing food adulteration, particularly focusing on organic food and geographical indications. Through these collaborations, Watson aims to foster joint communication and dissemination activities, ensuring that partners’ collective efforts have a broader impact and reach a wider audience. Watson recognises the value of sharing knowledge and expertise with other projects in the field and intends to explore opportunities for joint validation campaigns. Furthermore, Watson recognises the importance of liaising with other projects funded in similar domains. Through knowledge exchange and technology transfer, the project aims to leverage the expertise and experiences of these projects to enhance its own outcomes. This collaboration will also extend to the development of joint policy recommendations at both national and EU levels, aiming to influence and shape policies that support the Farm-to-Fork and Food 2030 strategies. Additionally, Watson actively participates in public fora and working groups dedicated to systemic innovations in the agrifood sector, further expanding the visibility and impact of the project.

2.4 Project visibility – commitments and responsibilities

The outcomes of this project will be made possible through the generous financial support provided by the European Union (EU). Therefore, it is essential that all Watson’s communication and dissemination materials prominently feature the EU emblem and include specific wording to acknowledge the EU's contribution.

The EU emblem, which consists of a circle of 12 golden stars on a blue background, must be displayed visibly and appropriately in all project-related materials. This emblem serves as a visual representation of the EU's support and must be used in accordance with the guidelines provided by the EU. In addition to the EU emblem, a specific wording should be included to acknowledge the EU's financial support. In the case of the Watson project, the “Funded by the European Union” acknowledgement is being used (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Acknowledgement of EU funding

Moreover, Watson communication or dissemination activities include the following disclaimer:

*“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA).
Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”*

This is shown below, in the example of Watson’s website homepage (Figure 4). By adhering to the EU's requirements for acknowledgement, the project demonstrates its gratitude for the EU's support and helps raise awareness about the EU's investment in research and innovation initiatives. It also ensures transparency and accountability in the use of EU funds, while promoting the visibility and credibility of the project's outcomes within the EU and beyond.

In addition, communication and dissemination activities must be in line with the Grant Agreement - Article 17 – “Communication, Dissemination and Visibility”, and Annex 5 – “Specific Rules on Communication, Dissemination and Visibility”.

Figure 4: Acknowledgement of EU funding on Watson website

2.5 Update of the communication and dissemination channels

Watson communication and dissemination strategy has been revised and updated to enhance its reach, engagement and overall impact across the target groups. This updated strategy reflects a more targeted and multi-dimensional approach, ensuring that the project's outcomes are effectively communicated to a diverse audience, including industry stakeholders, policymakers, academia and the broader public.

One of the significant updates to the strategy involves a stronger emphasis on leveraging digital tools, intensifying the use of the project website and social media (e.g. concise and visually engaging infographics and short videos have been created for both channels), holding/attending online workshops and liaison

meetings, publishing electronic articles mainly in partner's websites but also in magazines, and producing e-newsletters to disseminate project findings and outcomes.

As outlined in section 3 (report on communication and dissemination activities), the Watson website is performing quite well, indicating that the initial strategy and its implementation have been effective. SAH, with the support of other partners, will continue to monitor and enhance the site to ensure it remains aligned with the project's needs. Potential improvements include increasing the accessibility of materials and results obtained so far, increasing our Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) performance, and reorganising the menus to highlight certain elements as the project evolves. Moving forward, the news section will continue to play a crucial role in keeping target audiences informed through concise summaries of key results, activities and achievements. The project will rely on the collaboration of various partners who are well-positioned to provide regular updates on their activities.

Regarding the use of social media platforms, given LinkedIn's remarkable performance, more focus will be placed on leveraging this platform's features. By analysing the occupation data (industry and job function) of followers, Watson can better understand audience needs and tailor future posts accordingly. This data could also be used for targeted sponsored campaigns to reach specific sub-groups identified by their industry, role or seniority level. While LinkedIn will be prioritized, X (Twitter), Instagram, and Facebook will continue to be used to share new website content and share relevant updates from partners. This approach will maintain engagement with the smaller audiences active on these platforms that are not on LinkedIn. Additionally, the YouTube channel will continue to be used to share videos that visually summarise the project's achievements and other relevant information.

On the other hand, according to the initial plan, three additional newsletters will be published during the remainder of the project:

- 4th newsletter, scheduled for February 2025.
- 5th newsletter, scheduled for August 2025.
- 6th newsletter, scheduled for February 2026.

As well as improvements to the website, it is also planned to improve the newsletter, mainly its structure and an optimisation of the content by adding only relevant activities and sorting by type of activity and date. To reach a wider audience, both the full newsletter and the individual news pieces will be shared through social media.

Additionally, Watson will continue organising dissemination events, expecting to hold at least one workshop in each pilot site. These workshops will allow partners to present the pilot developments to the relevant

community and stakeholders. Partners involved in the demonstrator will take the lead in developing the content, engaging the relevant stakeholders and delivering the workshops in the local language, with organisational and strategic support from SAH and LIC. Also, partners will continue to present Watson and distribute dissemination materials at relevant events.

Regarding the establishment of synergies with similar projects, Watson is mainly clustering with two related initiatives, <https://theros-project.eu/> and [ALLIANCE](#), which will lead to regular meetings and joint activities. In addition, Watson recently held a meeting involving other H2020/Horizon Europe projects that are members of the [Sustainable Food System Innovation Platform](#), of which Watson is also part of. Some of the managing projects attending the meeting were [EU4Advice](#), [FAIRCHAIN](#), [COREnet](#) and [WASTELESS](#). The meeting was also joined by projects that are not members of the platform, such as the [EU-FarmBook](#) and the [Oren Project](#). The synergy between these diverse initiatives contributes to paving the way for innovative solutions and impactful outcomes in the agriculture and food sectors.

The Watson project has also expanded its academic and scientific outreach. The consortium has been actively involved in presenting their research findings at international conferences, symposiums, and other academic events, as outlined in detail in chapter 3.1 below. In addition, the project prioritises the publication of research findings in high-impact, open-access scientific journals, ensuring that the knowledge generated will be accessible to all and foster further research and development in the field of food authenticity and transparency. An abstract and a poster from a Watson workshop were included in the conference proceedings “International Scientific Conference – Global commodity chains from a risk assessment perspective”, entitled “Improving Global Commodity Chains: A Technological Framework for Enhanced Food Quality Control and Transparency” and prepared by INT.

Overall, the updated strategy places a greater focus on targeted stakeholder engagement. Understanding the diverse needs and expectations of different stakeholder groups, Watson has adopted a more nuanced approach to communication. For instance, industry-specific workshops have been organised to provide a platform for industry professionals to discuss potential collaborations and commercialisation opportunities; as well as key promotional materials (booklet) and articles have been written in several languages (Finnish, Slovene, Spanish, etc.).

3. Report on communication and dissemination activities

Following the initial months of Watson, which were primarily dedicated to establishing the project’s brand identity (D6.1) and crafting the initial communication and dissemination strategy (D6.2), the focus has

gradually shifted to building and promoting the Watson project across selected channels. As the project moved beyond its first year, the emphasis transitioned to the promotion of the project through regular production and updating of content related to Watson’s events and results. This is expected to continue until the project’s end, eventually leading to the broader deployment and sustainability of Watson’s innovations.

The communication and dissemination activities, carried out during the first 18 months of the project, are reported hereafter. It should be noted that this section includes only the status report on these activities. Thus, the exhaustive plan for activities is included in the previous Deliverable 6.2 (M4).

3.1 Project website

The Watson website is regularly updated and maintained to ensure the availability of the latest information and materials. User feedback and analytics are also monitored to continually improve the website's usability and address any potential issues. Since the website was launched in May 2023, the News and Outputs sections have been constantly updated and enriched with new content. So far, 31 posts have been published in this section. Also, improvements are being made, mainly correction and adaptation of these posts to a more appropriate format.

Some minor changes have also been implemented, based on ongoing developments within the project, such as the additional of JRC as a project partner at the beginning of 2024. Another example is the update of the FSH logo and information, since on June 5th, 2024, this partner has changed its organisation's official name and has proceeded with a rebranding to “Reframe.Food” (RFF). In addition, the contact information on both the footer and the Contact section have been updated. A visual overview of the key elements of the Watson website is provided below in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Watson website key elements: (a) home page, (b) use case information, (c) news and (d) contact section

So far, a total of 3,104 unique visitors have visited the Watson website from its launch in May 2024 to June 2024, receiving 10,476 views (Figure 6). This means that Watson website has far exceeded the set KPI (1,000 unique visitors/year).

Figure 6: Watson website metrics, May 2024 – June 2024

3.2 Social media

To enhance the reach of the project’s communication and dissemination efforts, Watson has established a strong presence across various social media platforms. Specifically, Watson partners have set up dedicated [LinkedIn](#) and [Facebook](#) pages, as well as [X \(Twitter\)](#), [Instagram](#) and [YouTube](#) accounts (Figure 7).

These channels play a pivotal role in the project's outreach efforts, since the use of multiple channels ensures a broader reach and enables the project to adapt its communication and dissemination approach to the preferences and behaviours of each target group. Thus, Watson intends to maintain an active online presence by consistently posting updates that showcase key insights and achievements related to the Watson project. Additionally, these platforms are instrumental in promoting upcoming events, activities and other initiatives planned throughout the project's duration.

So far, a significant number of posts on social media has been observed, as shown in Table 4. Social media enables Watson to share its research findings, publications and insights with a wider audience beyond traditional academic circles. It allows to reach a broader community, including policymakers, journalists and the general public, facilitating the dissemination of knowledge and increasing the project’s impact.

At the same time, Watson partners have been actively creating content and sharing posts about the project through their own organisations’ social media and private accounts. This not only allows for greater visibility of the project but is also very useful in reaching out to target audiences, as many of the partner organisations and their staff have extensive networks of contacts that are relevant to the project.

watson_horizon Following Message ...
88 posts 368 followers 1,197 following
WATSON
Horizon Europe project aiming to identify and prevent the spread of fraudulent practices in food systems
@ watsonproject.eu
Followed by excel4med and smartagrohob

Figure 7: Homepages of the Watson social media accounts

Table 4: Overview of Watson social media activities

Overview of Watson social media activities				
Social media channel	Account start date	Number of followers	Number of posts	Number of impressions/views
LinkedIn	18/06/2022	1,584	103	62,679 ¹
Facebook	08/11/2022	144	89	3,285
Instagram	03/11/2022	372	89	6,365
X (Twitter)	08/11/2022	937	89	15,041
YouTube	05/2023	32	8	754

According to certain metrics, such as the number of followers and the number of impressions/reactions received on Watson’s posts, LinkedIn is the most successful and best performing social media channel for Watson's communication and dissemination, followed by X (Twitter), Instagram and Facebook. Thus, as from August 22nd, 2023², we have reached 62,679 organic impressions (36,946 of these are unique impressions), 2,516 reactions, 41 comments and 38 reposts (see Figure 8 and Figure 9). This is mainly due to the fact that the primary target groups of the project, including the academic and scientific community, are widely present in this social network, so the content generated is of interest, useful, and can reach a wide variety of profiles.

¹ LinkedIn does not display analytics for periods longer than a year. As a result, the real total number of impressions will be higher than stated.

² The data relate to the period from August 22nd, 2023, to August 20th, 2024.

Figure 8: LinkedIn impressions (organic versus sponsored), August 2023 – August 2024

Figure 9: LinkedIn unique impressions, August 2023 – August 2024

Figure 10 showcases the best performing post on Watson’s LinkedIn according to the number of impressions, clicks on the post and reactions. This is a publication made on November 2nd, 2023, about the types of fraud in fish and seafood, which aims to raise awareness and provide information about the project using an infographic. The post reached 9,583 impressions, with 350 clicks and 175 reactions. This highlights the importance of including visual content, such as this infographic, in social media activities.

LinkedIn analytics also offer insights on the target audiences, mainly their industry and job roles, which can be useful to further tailor the content in line with their specific interests and needs. An analysis of these data shows that Watson followers are part of the target audiences identified in the Dissemination and Communication Strategy. As shown in Figure 11, about 40% of Watson’s LinkedIn followers work in higher education (14%) and research services (11.9%), and an additional 4.9%, 4.1% and 4.1% works in IT services

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and IT consulting, non-profit organisations, and food and beverage manufacturing. Other followers work in business consulting and services, farming, food and beverage services, and software development, which can also be interested in the Watson solution. Government administration is also one of the represented industries.

These sectors correspond to different categories of Watson's main target audiences. Indeed, "research", "business development" and "education" are indicated as main job functions by about 35% of followers, as shown in Figure 12.

Engaging on various social media channels allows us to connect with various target audiences. Although the content is generally the same for the different channels, there is some platform-specific customisation. For example, using different materials (attaching a document on LinkedIn, while including a picture on the other social media), adhering to different character limitations, and tagging key partners and organisations who are active on that specific platform.

Therefore, the strategy is to continue boosting Watson's LinkedIn page to reach the 5,000 followers proposed by the KPI, while trying to achieve better results in the other channels, especially X (Twitter), given that the KPI set for this platform is to reach 2,000 followers and so far, we have reached 937. To this end, we will better adapt the content to the different platforms (e.g., on Instagram we plan to produce more visual and less textual content, such as stories or live videos); and we will further promote Watson's YouTube channel by adding new videos produced within the framework of the project and, subsequently, disseminating them through the other social media channels.

Figure 10: Best performing post on Watson’s LinkedIn page

Follower demographics 🌐

Figure 11: LinkedIn follower demographics: Industry

Figure 12: LinkedIn follower demographics: Job function

3.3 Newsletters

Watson’s website offers a dedicated section for [newsletters](#) (Figure 13). In this way, website users can stay updated on the latest news, events and project developments. So far, the project has prepared and published three newsletters (available on Watson’s website):

- **Watson 1st Newsletter (March 2023 - August 2023)** on the kick-off meeting of the project, as well as on Watson's participation in various events.
 - According to Google Analytics, this newsletter has received 48 views on the project website.
- **Watson 2nd Newsletter (September 2023 - February 2024)** on Watson’s General Assembly, on its participation in various events, as well as on the “Watson Food Fraud Vulnerability Assessment” questionnaire.
 - According to Google Analytics, this newsletter has received 136 views on the project website.
- **Watson 3rd Newsletter (March 2024 - August 2024)** on Watson’s participation in various events, on several videos about food fraud produced within the project framework, as well as on Watson's appearance in various magazine and press articles.

Figure 13 Watson's newsletters

3.4 Media outlets and press releases

Media outlets and press releases are crucial for reaching a wider audience, including the public, industry professionals and policymakers. Since engaging with classic media channels helps to raise awareness, attract attention from industry and policy stakeholders, and promote the project's objectives and achievements, Watson recognises the importance of using these channels to share project information and engage with stakeholders. Therefore, the project is actively trying to be featured from time to time in various media, as shown in the different media posts featuring the project in Figure 14-17.

3.4.1 Watson on “Más de Uno Oviedo – Onda Cero”

On November 24th, 2023, ASINCAR broadcast the radio programme “Más de Uno Oviedo” from the Spanish radio station Onda Cero (Figure 14). The main objective was to provide testimonials and highlight the relevance of food quality labels, such as PGI, PDOs and other quality schemes.

Figure 14: Watson on the radio programme “Más de Uno Oviedo”

3.4.2 Watson on “Kehittyvä Elintarvike”

An article of the Watson project has been included in the [Finnish food trade magazine “Kehittyvä Elintarvike”](#), published on March 1st, 2024 (Figure 15). The article has been written by partners VTT, UPC and HAI.

Figure 15: Watson on the Finnish food trade magazine “Kehittyvä Elintarvike”

3.4.3 Watson on “La Nueva España”

The Spanish newspaper “La Nueva España” features Watson in this [press release available on its website](#), and published on March 28th, 2024 (Figure 16).

La Nueva España

Esto permitirá, por ejemplo, frenar de manera temprana los riesgos asociados a una alerta sanitaria o detectar un fraude que se esté produciendo por parte de algún actor de la cadena.

Con gran interés para la marca "Alimentos del Paraíso", y a modo de experiencias piloto, ASINCAR está participando en los proyectos europeos ALLIANCE y WATSON, ambos aprobados dentro del competitivo programa Horizonte Europa, donde se desarrollarán y testearán ampliamente novedosas tecnologías, como la Inteligencia Artificial, el Internet de las Cosas, Blockchain o sensores avanzados, para mejorar la trazabilidad y la autenticidad de las cadenas de valor alimenticias.

El proyecto ALLIANCE pone su foco en alimentos amparados bajo una marca de calidad (por ejemplo, IGP o DOP), mientras que WATSON es aplicable para todo tipo de alimentos.

Figure 16: Press release about Watson published by "La Nueva España"

3.4.4 Watson on "WIKIFARMER"

Watson has been highlighted in the [article "Safeguarding Food Integrity: Combatting Fraud Across EU Supply Chains"](#), published on the WIKIFARMER platform on April 2024 (Figure 17).

Figure 17: Article about Watson on WIKIFARMER

3.5 Articles and posts on partners' websites

Partners have actively been communicating Watson on their own organisations' websites. Below are some articles and posts featuring Watson that have been published on some of the partner organisations' websites (see Figure 18-25).

3.5.1 Several posts on BIO website

The following posts about Watson have been published on BIO website (Figure 18):

- [Generic post about Watson](#), published on March 9th, 2023.
- [Post about the participation in "Agriumbria 2023" fair](#), published on May 18th, 2023.
- [Post about Watson technical coordination meeting](#), published on April 15th, 2024.

Our Horizon EU project [WATSON](#) (ID: 101084265) officially launched on 1st March 2023!

Start: 1 March 2023 – End: 8 February 2026 Total fund € 9 744 008,35

45 Partners from 22 Countries join forces to develop tools to prevent food fraud across the food supply chain, raise consumer awareness about safety and value, leading to the adoption of healthier lifestyles and the development of sustainable food ecosystems.

WATSON is a flagship EU proposal that aims to develop a set of systems that provide greater transparency throughout a food product's journey, raise consumer awareness of food safety and value, promote healthier lifestyles, and create a sustainable food ecosystem. The technologies will be demonstrated in six different use cases in a number of key food supply chains across Europe, including olive oil, wine, honey, and other products.

Last week, BioCoS actively engaged in the technical coordination meeting of the EU WATSON project in London.

The relevant stakeholders optimized the food safety technological framework to hand over to the industry.

During the meeting, BioCoS showcased the advancements in the on-site DNA profiling of Olive Oil.

Figure 18: Watson posts on BIO website

3.5.2 Several posts on SAH website

The following posts about Watson have been published on SAH website (Figure 19):

- [Post about Watson kick-off meeting](#), published on March 15th, 2023.
- [Post about Watson](#) which is continuously available on its website, in the 'Research & Development' / 'European Projects' section.

Figure 19: Watson posts on SAH website

3.5.3 Article on INESC TEC website

INESC TEC wrote the [article “Watson: the European project that promotes traceability and tackles fraud in the food sector”](#), published on its website on April 4th, 2023 (Figure 20).

Figure 20: Watson article on INESC TEC website

3.5.4 Article on UCD website

On July 19th, 2023, UCD published on its website the [article “The era of robotic milking has arrived - Irish farms go digital”](#), featuring Watson (Figure 21).

“The era of robotic milking has arrived” - Irish farms go digital

Wednesday, 19 July, 2023

Dr Dimitrios Argyropoulos is Assistant Professor in the School of Biosystems and food engineering at University College Dublin. He is also the UCD programme director of the new masters in Digital Technology for Sustainable Agriculture and a principal investigator with the UCD Institute of Food and Health. Here he talks about smart farming and the digital transformation of agriculture.

Figure 21: Watson article on UCD website

3.5.5 Post on NTU website

On December 25th, 2023, NTU shared on its website a [post about its participation in the “51st Annual Food Science and Technology Conference”](#), where it showcased Watson (Figure 22).

Figure 22: Watson post on NTU website

3.5.6 Several articles on UNC website

The following articles about Watson have been published on UNC website (Figure 23):

- Article [“Watson, la campagna per prevenire e contrastare le frodi alimentari”](#), published on November 24th, 2023.
- Article [“Api e ambiente: un rapporto fortemente minacciato”](#), published on January 30th, 2024.
- Article [“Come difenderci dalle contraffazioni dell’olio di oliva”](#), published on February 6th, 2024.
- Article [“Vino, attenzione a frodi e contraffazioni”](#), published on April 2nd, 2024.
- Article [“Miele contraffatto: approvata la Direttiva colazione”](#), published on April 30th, 2024.
- Article [“Latte andato a male corretto con soda caustica e acqua ossigenata”](#), published on May 7th, 2024.
- Article [“Quali sono le frodi della carne più comuni?”](#), published on May 27th, 2024.
- Article [“Frodi sul vino: come riconoscerle”](#), published on June 5th, 2024.

Figure 23: Watson articles on UNC website

3.5.7 Several posts/articles on ZPS website

The following posts about Watson have been published on ZPS website (Figure 24):

- [Post about Watson](#), published on August 4th, 2023.
- An [article on milk fraud was published in ZPStest and ZPS website](#), on May 9th, 2024.
- An article on honey fraud, in occasion of the International Bee Day, published on May 20th, 2024.

Figure 24: Watson posts and articles on ZPS website

3.5.8 Several posts on EuroFIR website

The following posts about Watson have been published on EuroFIR website (Figure 25):

- Watson was included in [“Project Updates, October 2023”](#), published on September 25th, 2023, on EuroFIR website.
- Watson was included in [“Project Updates, February 2024”](#), published on February 11th, 2024, on EuroFIR website.

Figure 25: Watson posts on EuroFIR website

3.6 Promotional materials

Providing promotional materials for Watson events is a great way to create visibility and reinforce the project's brand identity. The materials, including a booklet, a branded USB stick and a kick-off tote bag, served as practical items that project partners can continue using to increase awareness, and further promote the project and its visibility. It should be noted that the booklet, the poster and the roll-up banner have been continuously updated to reflect any changes in the project or updates in the project progress, such as the additional of the JRC as a partner and the new RFF (formerly FSH) logo.

3.6.1 Booklet

The booklet provides essential information about the Watson project, including its objectives, key activities and anticipated outcomes. It features visually appealing designs, incorporating the project's logo, key visuals and relevant project images. The booklet is informative, concise and engaging, capturing the attention of the readers and encouraging them to learn more about the project. Excerpts from the booklet are provided in Figure 26.

Funding scheme: HORIZON-CL6-2022-FARM2FORK-01-11
EU Contribution: € 9,744,008
Total cost: € 11,221,383
Duration: 3 years, March 2023 – February 2026
Consortium: 45 partners across 20 EU & non-EU countries
Pilot sites: 6 use cases on agri-food value chains
Project Coordinator: University College Dublin

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Follow us on X for project updates.
 Use #watson_horizon to share your thoughts

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Figure 26: Excerpts from the Watson booklet: (a) cover page, (b) overview of project's technological integration, (c) partners and (d) project facts and contact information

3.6.2 Branded USB stick

The Watson branded USB stick (Figure 27) serves as a useful tool for storing and sharing project-related documents, reports, presentations or other digital resources. The USB stick is customised with the project logo and branding elements, ensuring its association with the project. Partners have preloaded the USB stick with materials or resources relevant to the project, making it even more valuable to the recipients.

3.6.3 Kick-off tote bag

The Watson tote bag given to partners during the kick-off in Dublin in March 2023 (Figure 28) provided a practical and eco-friendly way for project partners to carry their belongings during the event and beyond.

The tote bag features the project logo prominently, helping to increase its brand visibility and recognition. It has also been made from durable and sustainable materials to align with the project's focus on sustainability and environmental consciousness.

Figure 27: Watson USB stick

Figure 28: Watson kick-off tote bag

3.6.4 Poster

The Watson poster (Figure 29), measuring 100 cm x 70 cm and consisting of a single page, is suited for use as an informational focal point at fairs, events or booths rather than for distribution purposes.

3.6.5 Roll-up banner

The roll-up banner (Figure 30) of Watson provides a versatile, portable and cost-effective marketing tool to create project awareness, and effectively convey information in a visually appealing manner. Thus, partners have designed a 200 cm x 90 cm plastic roll-up, which includes basic information about the project, to use it during the project events or when participating in third-party workshops and events as promotional image of the project.

Figure 29: Watson poster

FACTS

Funding scheme: HORIZON-CL4-2022-FARM-FORUM-01-01
 EU Contribution: € 9.744.000
 Total cost: € 11.221.363
 Duration: 3 years, March 2023 - February 2026
 Consortium: 45 partners across 20 EU & non-EU countries
 Pilot sites: 8 pilot sites in agri-food value chains
 Project Coordinator: University College Dublin

Funded by
the European Union

Preventing food fraud through digital and intelligence-based technologies

Tackling counterfeiting of Portuguese wine

Preserving the authenticity of Spanish northwest PGI honey

Rapid Traceability of Extra Virgin Olive Oil with a Digital DNA Fingerprint

Identification of Possible Manipulations at All Stages of the Meat Chain

Improved Traceability of High - value Products in Cereal and Dairy Chain

Combating counterfeiting of Norwegian White Fish

CASE STUDIES AND VALIDATION CAMPAIGNS

Intelligence-based risk calculation
 Watson will implement an intelligence-based risk calculation approach to address the phenomenon of food fraud in a holistic way

Towards a digital passport for food products
 Watson will ensure traceability of food products and the sustainability of food chains

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Figure 30: Watson roll-up banner

3.7 Videos

A teaser video for the Watson project has been produced (Figure 31) and uploaded it on [Watson's YouTube channel](#). This video is a highly effective strategy to generate interest, anticipation and excitement among the target groups.

Figure 31: Watson teaser video

On the other hand, professor and food safety expert, Agostino Macrì, in collaboration with UNC, prepared seven videos talking about food fraud and other aspects related with Watson use case studies (

Figure 32). Although produced in Italian, the videos include automatically generated English subtitles, as they are available on [Watson's YouTube channel](#). A specific playlist has also been created to make it easier for the public to watch them all.

Figure 32: Video about fraud of methanol wine

3.8 Mini-series

In addition, throughout the duration of Watson, a TV mini-series will be produced in collaboration with our partner Euronews (EUN). The mini-series will serve as a platform for discussing the project's main challenges, necessary actions and outcomes. They will involve experts, stakeholders from the food chain industry and interested local communities. The aim is to raise awareness about Watson's activities and results while fostering discussions on relevant topics.

Conducted in parallel with the pilots, these mini-series will highlight the importance of data sharing in the food chain, specifically targeting transparency, traceability and authenticity. By showcasing suitable practices, they will demonstrate how data sharing directly impacts consumers. Additionally, the theme of "green jobs" will be explored, emphasising the employment opportunities and wealth generation associated with environmentally friendly practices within a more sustainable economy, particularly in relation to authentic food products. All the topics covered in the mini-series will be made available to the public through a dedicated section on the EUN website. Users will have access to additional content, including full interviews with experts and verified references to scientific articles.

3.9 Public deliverables and scientific publications

Both public deliverables and scientific publications serve distinct purposes in disseminating Watson's work, since public deliverables are tailored for a broader audience, emphasising the practical implications and applicability of the project's outcomes. To maximise the outreach and capture the interest of pertinent stakeholders, partners are committed to publishing public deliverables online, mainly using Watson's

website, to be shared with relevant organisations and used as reference materials for future projects and initiatives.

Recognising the critical role that publications play in amplifying the project's success, partners have explored potential channels for disseminating project-related news and have identified relevant journals that hold the potential to efficiently distribute the outcomes and findings of the Watson project. Table 5 includes relevant journals that are being targeted by the communication and dissemination strategy as the project progresses.

In addition, the consortium is preparing at least one special issue in one of those relevant journals, or in related journals. The high scientific profile of the participating academic and research institutes guarantees the success of these special issues, which will demonstrate the project's research achievements worldwide.

Table 5: Relevant journals targeted by Watson's consortium

Relevant journals for Watson
IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics
NATURE
IEEE Security & Privacy Journal
Springer - Discover Food Journal
Elsevier - Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment Journal
Elsevier - Smart Agricultural Technology Journal
Elsevier - Sustainable Horizons Journal

As previously noted, Watson aims to regularly publish papers in scientific journals throughout the project timeline. During the first half of the project, we have prepared an abstract included in the book of abstracts "International Scientific Conference – Global commodity chains from a risk assessment perspective", entitled "[Improving Global Commodity Chains: A Technological Framework for Enhanced Food Quality Control and Transparency](#)", written by Paraskevas Bourgos, Amalia Ntemou, Ioanna Drigkopoulou, Pantelis Lappas and Spyros Evangelatos, from INT (Figure 33). In addition, INT has also created a poster to disseminate Watson during this conference (Figure 34).

3.28 Improving Global Commodity Chains: A Technological Framework for Enhanced Food Quality Control and Transparency

Paraskevas Bourgos, Amalia Ntemou, Ioanna Drigkopoulou, Pantelis Lappas, Spyros Evangelatos

Netcompany-intrasoft

This poster presents a novel technological framework developed by Netcompany-Intrasoft (NCIS) to tackle challenges in global food supply chains, including food fraud and security, sustainability, traceability, and transparency issues. It integrates advanced blockchain technology, a digital food product passport as well as fosters evidence-based decision making through AI and ML for preventative interventions and actionable planning.

Central to this initiative is the deployment of blockchain solutions that ensure data integrity and traceability across the supply chain. This infrastructure supports real-time data accessibility and fraud prevention, establishing a trustworthy environment for all supply chain participants. Additionally, the framework includes the development of a digital food product passport technology and interface. This technology is essential for documenting and communicating detailed, tamper-proof information about food products throughout their journey from farm to table. Furthermore, an AI-enabled Early Warning and Decision Support System leverages predictive analytics to preemptively identify and mitigate risks of food fraud, enhancing decision-making processes and ensuring the reliability of food quality and safety.

The efficacy and adaptability of this technological framework are exemplified through its application in several Horizon Europe projects—FOODGUARD (GA No 101136542), WATSON (GA No 101084265), and ALLIANCE (GA No 101084188). These projects demonstrate how the framework's innovations are tailored to meet specific challenges within the food industry. NCIS has played a key role in deploying these technologies, showcasing its commitment to leveraging IT solutions to enhance global commodity chains and ensure a safer, more transparent global food system.

Figure 33: Watson abstract "Improving Global Commodity Chains: A Technological Framework for Enhanced Food Quality Control and Transparency"

Figure 34: Watson poster "Improving Global Commodity Chains: A Technological Framework for Enhanced Food Quality Control and Transparency"

On the other hand, Watson carried out the questionnaire “[Fraud vulnerability assessment in representative European agri-food supply chains](#)”, between November 2023 and March 2024 (

Fraud vulnerability assessment in representative European agri-food supply chains

The WATSON project recently carried out a [Fraud vulnerability assessment in representative European agri-food supply chains \(Nov 2023-Mar 2024\)](#). To further validate the results, we are now inviting experts and stakeholders to provide feedback on the draft report below. This consultation phase will end on April 30th.

To add a comment, click on the "+" next to the relevant sentence / paragraph. The first time you comment, you will be prompted to create a profile with name and email address. Kindly note that your chosen name will be displayed with your comments, and it cannot be changed without deleting the comment. The email address will not be displayed publicly, but it will be available to project partners. For further details please see the [privacy policy](#).

Figure 35). This comprehensive questionnaire was led by UCD and included 30 insightful questions, and its objective is to better understand the vulnerabilities across various stages of the supply chain. The questionnaire was completed by 119 stakeholders from 19 countries (Austria, Bulgaria, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, New Zealand, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovenija, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, The Netherlands and United Kingdom), representing the 6 Watson pilot agri-food value chains.

Figure 35: Watson questionnaire on food fraud vulnerability assessment

3.10 Events

Since the Watson consortium is highly committed to actively seeking opportunities to effectively share the project's overarching objectives and the tangible results it achieves, it has curated a thorough list of potential events that could serve as ideal venues for the project's participation and presentations in the future. These events span a range of relevant domains and are chosen with the intent of maximising the project's outreach, impact and visibility within the academic and industry communities.

Among the different types of events, the project prioritises workshops and conferences, since they are valuable platforms for sharing knowledge, exchanging ideas and engaging with stakeholders. These types of events provide opportunities for Watson to present its research findings, innovative solutions and advancements in the agrifood and technology sectors. Thus, Watson aims to actively participate in relevant workshops and conferences within those sectors at regional, national, European and international levels. During the first half of the project (M1-M18), Watson partners have participated in 52 events across Europe, of which 12 are events that have been (co-)organised within the framework of the project itself (see Table 6), and 40 are external events in which Watson has participated (see Table 7).

Table 6: Summary of events organised by Watson

Events organised by Watson		
Event	Date	Location
Liaison meeting between Watson and ALLIANCE projects	March 13 th -14 th , 2023	Dublin (Ireland)
Watson WP2 workshop for the fish supply chain	November 28 th , 2023	Online
Watson WP2 workshop for the honey supply chain	November 29 th , 2023	Asturias (Spain) and online
Watson WP2 workshops for the olive oil supply chain ³	November 2023 – February 2024	Crete (Greece)
Workshop “Digital services to promote the efficiency of the agrifood sector”	January 24 th , 2024	Asturias (Spain)
Watson WP2 workshop for the dairy supply chain	March 15 th , 2024	Online
Watson WP2 workshop for the wine supply chain	April 15 th , 2024	Online

³ This workshop was held on multiple dates, one of them during the “InnoDays 2023” conference.

Dissemination and Communication Strategy and Periodic Dissemination and Communication Report (Interim Report 2)

Liaison meeting between Watson, THEROS and ALLIANCE	May 17 th , 2024	Online
“INRAE open days”	May 23 rd -26 th , 2024	INRAE Clermont-Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes research centre (France)
Workshop "Solutions for Transparency and Integrity in the EU Food System" ⁴	May 27 th -29 th , 2024	Berlin (Germany)
“Food Fraud Unmasked 2024” Symposium	June 13 th -14 th , 2024	Dublin (Ireland)
“Sustainable Food System Innovation Platform WG Meeting”	July 23 rd , 2024	Online

Table 7: Summary of external events attended by Watson

External events attended by Watson			
Event	Partner(s) involved	Date	Location
TRUSTFOOD kick-off meeting	SAH	February 8 th , 2023	Patras (Greece)
Info-day “Funding, Networking and Technology Transfer Opportunities for Mature Research Groups of the Agricultural University”	SAH	February 16 th , 2023	Athens (Greece)
Seminar "Tips for a successful application in Horizon Europe / CL6"	SAH	February 22 nd , 2023	Athens (Greece)
PDA workshop on ongoing projects	PDA, ASI	February 23 rd , 2023	Oviedo (Spain)
“5 th VERDE.TEC 2023”	SAH	March 17 th -19 th , 2023	Athens (Greece)
“54 th edition of Agriumbria Fair”	BIO, CNR, APR, MIT	March 31 st - April 2 nd , 2023	Perugia (Italy)
“Salón Gourmets 2023 – 36 th International Fine Food and Beverages Fair”	ASI	April 17 th -20 th , 2023	Madrid (Spain)
“Beyond Expo”	SAH	May 24 th -26 th , 2023	Thessaloniki (Greece)
“7 th International ISEKI-Food Conference”	IFA	July 5 th -8 th , 2023	Paris (France)
Final transnational project meeting of Foster-xR	UCD	August 1 st -2 nd , 2023	Dublin (Ireland)
“Agri Innovation Expo 2023”	SAH, UCD	September 21 st -23 rd , 2023	Agricultural University of Athens (Greece)
“AGROPEC 2023 - 37 ^a Feria del Campo y de las Industrias Agrícolas, Ganaderas, Forestales y Pesqueras”	ASI	September 22 nd -24 th , 2023	Gijón (Spain)
Conference “Ensuring Safety, Preventing Waste”	UNC	September 29 th , 2023	Rome (Italy)
“Horizon Europe Informative Session”	ASI	November 15 th , 2023	Asturias (Spain)
Conference “InnoDays 2023”	BIO	November 25 th , 2023	Crete (Greece)

⁴ This workshop was held during the event “International Scientific Conference - Global commodity chains from a risk assessment perspective”.

Dissemination and Communication Strategy and Periodic Dissemination and Communication Report (Interim Report 2)

“Patras Innovation Quest - Competence Centres: Catalyst for the Development and Exploitation of Innovation”	SAH	November 25 th , 2023	Patras (Greece)
Conference “Modern Trends in Food Science and Human Nutrition”	SAH	December 6 th , 2023	Patras (Greece)
“51 st Annual Food Science and Technology Conference”	UCD	December 6 th -7 th , 2023	Ashtown (Ireland)
“FITUR 2024”	ASI, PDA	January 24 th -28 th , 2024	Madrid (Spain)
Conference “Bees and their precious contribution to the maintenance of biodiversity”	UNC	January 25 th , 2024	Rome (Italy)
“TALLHEDA kick-off meeting”	SAH	January 29 th , 2024	Athens (Greece)
“30 th AGROTICA 2024”	SAH, SYN	February 1 st -4 th , 2024	Thessaloniki (Greece)
“SALENOR Fair 2024”	ASI	February 19 th -21 st , 2024	Avilés (Spain)
Conference “Is EU trade policy compatible with the Green Deal?”	ZPS	March 15 th , 2024	Ljubljana (Slovenia)
“ALIMENTARIA 2024”	ASI	March 18 th -21 st , 2024	Barcelona (Spain)
“TRANSFIERE 2024 – 13 th European Meeting on Science, Technology, and Innovation”	ASI	March 20 th -22 nd , 2024	Málaga (Spain)
“1 st Automation and Robotics”	SYN	April 12 th -14 th , 2024	Athens (Greece)
“Salón Gourmets 2024 – 37 th International Fine Food and Beverages Fair”	IGP, ASI	April 22 nd -25 th , 2024	Madrid (Spain)
“Food 4 Future – Expo FoodTech”	ASI	April 23 rd -25 th , 2024	Bilbao (Spain)
“Food and Drink Science Member Interest Group meeting”	UCD	May 2 nd , 2024	Online
“Feria de la Ascensión”	IGP	May 10 th -12 th , 2024	Oviedo (Spain)
Finnish food congress “Elintarvikepäivä”	VTT	May 14 th , 2024	Helsinki (Finland)
“Second AIPnD Conference, Diagnostics in the Agri-food sector, non-destructive investigations, regulations and needs”	UNC	May 16 th -17 th , 2024	University of Parma, Department of Food and Drug Science - Congress Centre - Parma (Italy)
“Customer Centricity”	UNC	May 21 st , 2024	Rome (Italy)
“International Scientific Conference - Global commodity chains from a risk assessment perspective”	INT, UCD, RFF, HUB, BIO	May 27 th -29 th , 2024	Berlin (Germany)
“Oenotrace project meeting”	UCD	June 3 rd -4 th , 2024	Florence (Italy)
“We Make Future – International Trade Fair and Festival on Innovation: AI, Tech and Digital”	UNC	June 13 th -15 th , 2024	Bologna (Italy)
“Mercado de la Paz”	IGP	July 3 rd -4 th , 2024	Madrid (Spain)
“III Jornada Interfacultad de Nutrición y Alimentos - Sostenibilidad en la Cadena de Suministro Alimentario”	CNR	July 25 th , 2024	Universidad Autónoma de Chile (Chile)
“Feria Internacional de Muestras de Gijón”	IGP	August 12 th , 2024	Gijón (Spain)

More details about each event can be seen below.

3.10.1.1 TRUSTFOOD kick-off meeting

On February 2023, SAH attended the TRUSTFOOD (Digital Europe project) kick-off meeting, held in Patras (Greece), where it presented Watson (Figure 36).

Figure 36: Watson at TRUSTFOOD kick-off meeting

3.10.1.2 Info-day “Funding, Networking and Technology Transfer Opportunities for Mature Research Groups of the Agricultural University”

SAH introduced Watson in the info-day “Funding, Networking and Technology Transfer Opportunities for Mature Research Groups of the Agricultural University”, held in Athens (Greece) on February 16th, 2023 (Figure 37).

Figure 37: Watson at the info-day “Funding, Networking and Technology Transfer Opportunities for Mature Research Groups of the Agricultural University”

3.10.1.3 Seminar “Tips for a successful application in Horizon Europe / CL6”

On February 22nd, 2023, SAH organised the seminar “Tips for a successful application in Horizon Europe / CL6”, presenting Watson to the attendees.

3.10.1.4 PDA workshop on ongoing projects

On February 23rd, 2023, PDA organised, with the support of ASINCAR, a workshop related to its ongoing European projects, including Watson (Figure 38).

Figure 38: Watson at PDA's workshop

3.10.1.5 Liaison meeting between Watson and ALLIANCE projects

Watson clustered with the EU-funded project ALLIANCE during Watson's kick-off meeting, held in Dublin (Ireland) on March 13th-14th, 2023 (Figure 39).

Figure 39: Liaison meeting between Watson and ALLIANCE projects

3.10.1.6 "5th VERDE.TEC 2023"

SAH presented Watson at the "5th VERDE.TEC 2023" exhibition, held in Athens (Greece) on March 17th-19th, 2023 (Figure 40).

Figure 40: Watson at the “5th VERDE.TEC 2023”

3.10.1.7 “54th edition of Agriumbria Fair”

BIO, IBBR-CNR, APROL UMBRIA and MIT showcased Watson’s olive oil use case study during the “54th edition of Agriumbria Fair”, celebrated in Perugia (Italy) on March 31st-April 2nd, 2023 (Figure 41).

Figure 41: Watson at 54th Agriumbria Fair

3.10.1.8 “Salón Gourmets 2023 – 36th International Fine Food and Beverages Fair”

ASINCAR presented Watson in the “Salón Gourmets 2023 – 36th International Fine Food and Beverages Fair”, which was held in Madrid (Spain) on April 17th-20th, 2023 (Figure 42).

Figure 42: Watson at “Salón Gourmets 2023”

3.10.1.9 “Beyond Expo”

SAH and RFF presented Watson at “Beyond Expo”, held in Thessaloniki (Greece) on May 24th-26th, 2023 (Figure 43).

Figure 43: Watson at “Beyond Expo”

3.10.1.10 “7th International ISEKI-Food Conference”

IFA presented Watson under the theme "Empowering the Next Generation of Food Research, Education, and Industry" during the “7th International ISEKI-Food Conference”, celebrated in Paris (France) on July 5th-8th, 2023 (Figure 44).

Figure 44: Watson at the “7th International ISEKI-Food Conference”

3.10.1.11 Final transnational project meeting of Foster-xR

The project coordinator, Dr. Dimitrios Argyropoulos (UCD), promoted Watson during the final transnational project meeting of the Foster-xR project, held in Dublin (Ireland) on August 1st-2nd, 2023 (Figure 45). During the event, Dr. Dimitrios Argyropoulos hosted Vasilis Valdramidis, the coordinator of EXCEL4MED, another Horizon Europe-funded project.

Figure 45: Watson at the final transnational project meeting of Foster-xR

3.10.1.12 “Agri Innovation Expo 2023”

SAH and UCD showcased Watson at the “Agri Innovation Expo 2023”, which took place during September 21st-23rd, 2023, at the Agricultural University of Athens (Greece) (Figure 46).

Figure 46: Watson at “Agri Innovation Expo 2023”

3.10.1.13 “AGROPEC 2023 - 37ª FERIA del Campo y de las Industrias Agrícolas, Ganaderas, Forestales y Pesqueras”

ASINCAR showcased Watson at “AGROPEC 2023 - 37ª FERIA del Campo y de las Industrias Agrícolas, Ganaderas, Forestales y Pesqueras” fair, held on September 22nd-24th, 2023, in Gijón (Spain).

3.10.1.14 Conference “Ensuring Safety, Preventing Waste”

UNC presented Watson at the conference “Ensuring Safety, Preventing Waste”, organised by the Council of the Order of Food Technologists at the Capitol Hall of the Senate of the Republic, and held in Rome (Italy), on September 29th, 2023 (Figure 47).

Figure 47: Watson at “Ensuring Safety, Preventing Waste” conference

3.10.1.15 “Horizon Europe Informative Session”

ASINCAR showcased Watson at the “Horizon Europe Informative Session” organised by Agencia Sekuens and CDTI Innovación - Centro para el Desarrollo Tecnológico y la Innovación on November 15th, 2023, in Asturias (Spain) (Figure 48). The event included a dynamic round table, where several regional organisations shared their experience in Cluster 6 approved projects. Members from IGP were also in the audience.

Figure 48: Watson at “Horizon Europe Informative Session”

3.10.1.16 “Patras Innovation Quest - Competence Centres: Catalyst for the Development and Exploitation of Innovation”

On November 25th, 2023, SAH presented Watson in “Patras Innovation Quest - Competence Centres: Catalyst for the Development and Exploitation of Innovation”, held in Patras (Greece) (Figure 49).

Figure 49: Watson at “Patras Innovation Quest”

3.10.1.17 Watson WP2 workshop for the fish supply chain

On November 28th, 2023, the Watson WP2 workshop for the fish supply chain was held online (Figure 50).

This workshop was hosted by UCD, with participation from SIN, HER, DOF, ESP and RFF.

Figure 50: Watson WP2 workshop for the fish supply chain

3.10.1.18 Watson WP2 workshop for the honey supply chain

On November 29th, 2023, ASINCAR and IGP Miel de Asturias organised a hybrid Watson WP2 workshop to identify vulnerable nodes in the regional protected geographical indication (PGI) honey supply chain (Figure 51).

Figure 51: Watson WP2 workshop for the honey supply chain

3.10.1.19 Watson WP2 workshops for the olive oil supply chain

BIO has organised, in collaboration with UCD, several Watson WP2 workshops between November 2023 and February 2024, both in Greece and in Italy (Figure 52). For instance, the “Olive Oil Supply Chain Vulnerability Assessment” workshop, held during the “InnoDays 2023” conference in Crete (Greece) on November 25th, 2023; and two "Olive Oil Quality and Authenticity, from Field to Store" workshops, held on February 2nd and 3rd, 2024, both in Crete (Greece).

Figure 52: Watson workshop “Olive Oil Supply Chain Vulnerability Assessment”

3.10.1.20 Conference “Modern Trends in Food Science and Human Nutrition”

On December 6th, 2023, SAH showcased Watson at the conference "Modern Trends in Food Science and Human Nutrition", co-organised by the PSEK Region of Western Greece, SEVT and the Greek Technology Platform “Food for Life”. The event was hosted at the conference centre of the Hellenic Open University (HOU), in Patras (Greece) (Figure 53). During the event, SAH met with SEVT members and researchers to discuss food sector’s challenges and opportunities.

Figure 53: Watson at “Modern Trends in Food Science and Human Nutrition” conference

3.10.1.21 “51st Annual Food Science and Technology Conference”

UCD presented Watson at the “51st Annual Food Science and Technology Conference” in Teagasc (Ireland) on December 6th-7th, 2023 (Figure 54). The conference was organised by the Institute of Food Science & Technology of Ireland (IFSTI).

Figure 54: Watson at “51st Annual Food Science and Technology Conference”

3.10.1.22 Workshop “Digital services to promote the efficiency of the agrifood sector”

On January 24th, 2024, ASINCAR showcased Watson at its technical workshop “Digital services to promote the efficiency of the agrifood sector”, held in Asturias (Spain) (Figure 55).

Figure 55: Watson at “Digital services to promote the efficiency of the agrifood sector” workshop

3.10.1.23 “FITUR 2024”

ASINCAR and PDA presented Watson at “FITUR 2024” fair, held on January 24th-28th, 2024, in Madrid (Spain) (Figure 56).

Figure 56: Watson at “FITUR 2024”

3.10.1.24 Conference “Bees and their precious contribution to the maintenance of biodiversity”

Watson was presented by UNC at the conference “Bees and their precious contribution to the maintenance of biodiversity”, held at Rome (Italy), on January 25th, 2024 (Figure 57).

Figure 57: Watson at “Bees and their precious contribution to the maintenance of biodiversity” conference

3.10.1.25 “TALLHEDA kick-off meeting”

SAH presented Watson at the kick-off meeting of the Horizon Europe-funded project TALLHEDA, on January 29th, 2024 (Figure 58).

Figure 58: Watson at “TALLHEDA kick-off meeting”

3.10.1.26 “30th AGROTICA 2024”

SAH and SYN showcased Watson during the celebration of “30th AGROTICA 2024” fair, held on February 1st-4th, 2024, in Thessaloniki (Greece) (Figure 59).

Figure 59: Watson at “30th AGROTICA 2024”

3.10.1.27 “SALENOR Fair 2024”

ASINCAR presented Watson at the “SALENOR Fair 2024”, held on February 19th-21st, 2024, in Avilés (Spain) (Figure 60).

Figure 60: Watson at “SALENOR Fair 2024”

3.10.1.28 Watson WP2 workshop for the dairy supply chain

On March 15th, 2024, the Watson WP2 workshop for the dairy supply chain was held online (Figure 61). This workshop has been organised by VTT, UPC and HAI, in collaboration with UCD.

Figure 61: Watson WP2 workshop for the dairy supply chain

3.10.1.29 Conference “Is EU trade policy compatible with the Green Deal?”

ZPS showcased Watson at the conference "Is EU trade policy compatible with the Green Deal?", organised on March 15th, 2024, in Ljubljana (Slovenia) by the Slovene Consumer's Organisation, the European consumer organisation BEUC and the European Commission Representation in The Republic of Slovenia at the European Union House (Figure 62).

Figure 62: Watson at “Is EU trade policy compatible with the Green Deal?”

3.10.1.30 “ALIMENTARIA 2024”

ASINCAR presented Watson at “ALIMENTARIA 2024”, held on March 18th-21st, 2024, in Barcelona (Spain) (Figure 63).

Figure 63: Watson at “ALIMENTARIA 2024”

3.10.1.31 “TRANSFIERE 2024”

ASINCAR showcased Watson at the forum “TRANSFIERE 2024 – 13th European Meeting on Science, Technology, and Innovation”, celebrated on March 20th-22nd, 2024, in Málaga (Spain) (Figure 64).

Figure 64: Watson at “TRANSFIERE 2024”

3.10.1.32 “1st Automation and Robotics”

SYN presented Watson at the “1st Automation and Robotics” exhibition in Athens (Greece), which took place on April 12th-14th, 2024 (Figure 65).

Figure 65: Watson at “1st Automation and Robotics”

3.10.1.33 Watson WP2 workshop for the wine supply chain

On April 15th, 2024, INESC TEC and ADVID, with the support of DECO and UCD, held online the Watson workshop for the Portuguese wine pilot (Figure 66).

Figure 66: Watson workshop for the Portuguese wine pilot

3.10.1.34 “Salón Gourmets 2024 – 37th International Fine Food and Beverages Fair”

IGP and ASINCAR presented Watson in the “Salón Gourmets 2024 – 37th International Fine Food and Beverages Fair”, which was held on April 22nd-25th, 2024, in Madrid (Spain) (Figure 67).

Figure 67: Watson at “Sal3n Gourmets 2024 – 37th International Fine Food and Beverages Fair”

3.10.1.35 “Food 4 Future – Expo FoodTech”

ASINCAR showcased Watson at the “Food 4 Future – Expo FoodTech”, celebrated on April 23rd-25th, 2024, in Bilbao (Spain) (Figure 68).

Figure 68: Watson at “Food 4 Future – Expo FoodTech”

3.10.1.36 “Food and Drink Science Member Interest Group meeting”

UCD presented Watson at the online event “Food and Drink Science Member Interest Group meeting”, held on May 2nd, 2024 (Figure 69).

Figure 69: Watson at “Food and Drink Science MIG”

3.10.1.37 “Feria de la Ascensión”

On May 10th-12th, 2024, IGP attended the Ascension Fair, a festival of tourist interest in the Principality of Asturias (Spain), where it distributed promotional material of Watson (Figure 70).

Figure 70: Watson at “Feria de la Ascensión”

3.10.1.38 Finnish food congress “Elintarvikepäivä”

VTT presented Watson at the Finnish food congress “Elintarvikepäivä”, held on May 14th, 2024, in Helsinki (Finland) (Figure 71).

Figure 71: Watson at Finnish Food congress “Elintarvikepäivä”

3.10.1.39 “Second AIPnD Conference, Diagnostics in the Agri-food sector, non-destructive investigations, regulations and needs”

UNC presented Watson at the "Second AIPnD Conference, Diagnostics in the Agri-food sector, non-destructive investigations, regulations and needs", held at the University of Parma, Department of Food and Drug Science - Congress Centre - Parma (Italy), on May 16th-17th, 2024 (Figure 72).

Figure 72: Watson at “Second AIPnD Conference”

3.10.1.40 Liaison meeting between Watson, THEROS and ALLIANCE

Watson attended the liaison meeting with the EU-funded projects THEROS and ALLIANCE. This meeting, held online on May 17th, 2024, set the stage for a series of robust activities, towards strengthening the fortifying food safety measures and combating the insidious spread of fraudulent practices within the food sector (Figure 73).

Figure 73: Liaison meeting between Watson, THEROS and ALLIANCE

3.10.1.41 “Customer Centricity”

UNC presented Watson at the “Customer Centricity” annual event, which took place in Rome (Italy), on May 21st, 2024 (Figure 74).

Figure 74: Watson at “Customer Centricity”

3.10.1.42 “INRAE open days”

From May 23rd-26th, 2024, Watson was showcased during the open days organised by INRAE Clermont-Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes research centre (Figure 75).

Figure 75: Watson at “INRAE open days”

3.10.1.43 “International Scientific Conference - Global commodity chains from a risk assessment perspective”

On May 27th-29th, 2024, project partners UCD, RFF, HUB, INT and BIO presented Watson at the “International Scientific Conference - Global commodity chains from a risk assessment perspective”, organised by the Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung (BfR) in Berlin (Germany). During the conference, Watson hosted the workshop "Solutions for Transparency and Integrity in the EU Food System", organised by HUB's Agri-food Chain Management Group and the MRI's Department of Safety and Quality of Meat (Figure 76).

Figure 76: Watson at “Global commodity chains from a risk assessment perspective” conference / Watson workshop “Solutions for Transparency and Integrity in the EU Food System”

3.10.1.44 “Oenotrace project meeting”

UCD participated in the meeting of the EU-funded project Oenotrace, held in Florence (Italy), on June 3rd-4th 2024 where it had the opportunity to present Watson (Figure 77).

Figure 77: Watson at “Oenotrace project meeting”

3.10.1.45 Conference “Food Fraud Unmasked 2024 Symposium”

UCD presented Watson’s work entitled "Food Fraud Vulnerability Assessment of the Honey Supply Chain" at the “Food Fraud Unmasked 2024 Symposium” for early-stage career scientists, held at UCD in Dublin (Ireland) on June 13th-14th, 2024 (Figure 78).

Figure 78: Watson at “Food Fraud Unmasked 2024 Symposium”

3.10.1.46 “We Make Future – International Trade Fair and Festival on Innovation: AI, Tech and Digital”

UNC showcased Watson during “We Make Future – International Trade Fair and Festival on Innovation: AI, Tech and Digital”, held in Bologna (Italy) on June 13th-15th, 2024 (Figure 79).

Figure 79: Watson at “We Make Future”

3.10.1.47 “Mercado de la Paz”

On July 3rd-4th, 2024, IGP exhibited Watson at “Mercado de la Paz” (Madrid, Spain) by distributing promotional material to all those who came to the stand (Figure 80).

Figure 80: Watson at “Mercado de la Paz”

3.10.1.48 “Sustainable Food System Innovation Platform WG Meeting”

On July 23rd, 2024, Watson joined the “Sustainable Food System Innovation Platform WG Meeting” as one of the managing projects of the Sustainable Food System Innovation Platform (Figure 81). The Horizon 2020/Horizon Europe projects EU4Advice, FAIRCHAIN, COREnet and WASTELESS also attended the meeting as managing projects. In addition, the EU-FarmBook and Oren Project joined the meeting.

Figure 81: Watson at “Sustainable Food System Innovation Platform WG Meeting”

3.10.1.49 “III Jornada Interfacultad de Nutrición y Alimentos - Sostenibilidad en la Cadena de Suministro Alimentario”

On July 25th, 2024, CNR presented Watson during the conference “III Jornada Interfacultad de Nutrición y Alimentos - Sostenibilidad en la Cadena de Suministro Alimentario”, held in the Autonomous University of

Chile (Chile). The seminar on the Watson approach attracted great interest from public control authorities, universities and stakeholders in Chilean food production (Figure 82).

Figure 82: Watson at “III Jornada Interfacultad de Nutrición y Alimentos”

3.10.1.50 “Feria Internacional de Muestras de Gijón”

On August 12th, 2024, IGP showcased Watson at the International Trade Fair of Gijón (Spain). In addition, a live radio programme was broadcast on the Spanish radio station “Onda Cero” with participants from different areas, such as politics (General Director of Rural Development of the Regional Ministry) and nutrition, where the Watson project was presented (Figure 83).

Figure 83: Watson at “Feria Internacional de Muestras de Gijón”

Table 8 provides a comprehensive overview of the various communication and dissemination tools employed by Watson to engage with different stakeholder groups. Each tool is aligned with specific audiences to maximise the reach and impact of the project's outcomes.

Table 8: Mapping of Watson tools and targeted stakeholders

Mapping of tools and targeted stakeholders							
Tools	General public	Policymakers	Industry	Scientific community	Other research projects	Agrifood organisations	Media
Webpage	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Social media	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Press releases	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Events, workshops and conferences	✓		✓	✓	✓		
Peer-reviewed journals	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
Newsletters	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Deliverables			✓	✓	✓		
Videos	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Plenary meetings	✓					✓	
Policy papers		✓				✓	

4. Communication and dissemination monitoring

Effective monitoring of communication and dissemination activities is crucial for ensuring the success and impact of Watson. By closely tracking partners' efforts and outcomes, partners can assess progress, identify areas for improvement, and maximise the project's visibility and reach. To facilitate this process, the WP6 leaders have developed a comprehensive Excel file that serves as a centralised tool for monitoring and evaluating all communication and dissemination activities of all partners.

Watson's monitoring Excel file (Figure 84) is structured to capture key information and metrics related to communication and dissemination efforts. To carry out continuous monitoring, there are separate sheets for

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each 6-month period. In each one of them, there are columns focusing on different aspects of our activities, including:

- (a) Fill in Instructions
- (b) Reporting Period and Corresponding Month (M1-M6, M7-M12...)
- (c) No. of Action-
- (d) Partner
- (e) Date of Activity
- (f) Place of Activity
- (g) Type of Activity
- (h) Modality (In-Person/Online)
- (i) Description
- (j) Activity Link

No. of Act	Partner (Choose)	Date of activity	Place of activity	Type of activity (Choose)	Was the activity online	Description	Activity link
1	1. UNIVERSITY COLLEGE DUBLIN, NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, DUBLIN	example 1/11/2022	Brussels, Belgium	Participation to conference	In-Person	Press release	
2	14. ASOCIACION DE INVESTIGACION DE INDUSTRIAS CARNICAS DEL PRINCIPADO DE ASTURIAS	19-21/02/2024	Avilés, Asturias	Participation to fairs	In-Person	SALENOR 2024 fair, the Northern Spain Food ai	https://www.salenor.es/
3	WATSON Official Pages	3/1/2024	Online	Social media (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and Instagram)	Online	Exciting Collaborations and Knowledge Sha	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7169375465139101697
4	WATSON Official Pages	3/8/2024	Online	Social media (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and Instagram)	Online	The "IGP Miel de Asturias " (PGI Honey from A	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7173813937372356609
5	WATSON Official Pages	3/15/2024	Online	Social media (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and Instagram)	Online	Between 19-21 February 2024, ASINCAR partic	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7174393721868718080
6	14. ASOCIACION DE INVESTIGACION DE INDUSTRIAS CARNICAS DEL PRINCIPADO DE ASTURIAS	18-21/03/2024	Barcelona	Participation to fairs	In-Person	ALIMENTARIA 2024 international Food fair (Ma	https://www.alimentaria.com/visitar/
7	WATSON Official Pages	3/22/2024	Online	Social media (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and Instagram)	Online	Exciting Announcement! 🎉📢 Our 2nd W	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7176916216375091200
8	14. ASOCIACION DE INVESTIGACION DE INDUSTRIAS CARNICAS DEL PRINCIPADO DE ASTURIAS	3/28/2024	Online	Press release	Online	Asincar: Tecnología para asegurar la trazabili	https://www.lne.es/asturias-rural/2024/03/28/asincar-tecnologia-asegurar-trazabilidad-alimentos-100150061.html
9	WATSON Official Pages	3/29/2024	Online	Social media (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and Instagram)	Online	Exciting News from the Watson Project! 📢	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7179458721041760256
10	WATSON Official Pages	4/3/2024	Online	Social media (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and Instagram)	Online	Watson project was presented at an event ent	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7181176650829639681

Figure 84: Watson communication and dissemination monitoring Excel

4.1 Communication and dissemination KPIs

On the other hand, defining KPIs to assess the progress of dissemination and communication in line with the overall project’s approach is important to closely monitor the progress of Watson activities and measure their impact. A set of KPIs (Table 9), which address communication and dissemination activities, is being monitored and managed by the partners involved in such activities. This allows corrective measures to be

taken and enforced, whenever the performance and progress marked by the consortium are not aligned with the set objectives.

Table 9: Watson communication and dissemination KPIs

Watson communication and dissemination KPIs			
Activity	KPI	Target value	Status (M18)
Watson branded material	No. of brochures/booklets distributed	>200/year	240/year (4-5 booklets/event)
	No. of posters produced	2	2
	No. of roll-up banners produced	1	1
e-Newsletter	No. of newsletters	6	3
Website	No. of unique visitors	>3,000 >1,000/year	3,104
Social media	No. of followers on X (Twitter)	>2,000	937
	No. of followers on LinkedIn	>5,000	1,584
	No. of followers on Instagram	>500	372
	No. of followers on Facebook	>300	144
	No. of posts	>200 (5-6 posts/month)	370 (5-6 posts/month)
Watson Workshops	No. of training workshops for consumers and food safety authorities	3	Scheduled for the 2 nd Reporting Period.
	No. of workshops for stakeholders	6	6
	No. of participants	>20-25/workshop	128 in total 33 (wine workshop) 24 (olive oil workshop) 19 (fish workshop) 15 (honey workshop) 12 (dairy workshop) 25 (BfR workshop)
Other Watson events	No. of training activities organised in schools and neighbours promoting consumer awareness actions for food authenticity by the consumer associations of Watson, along with the organisation of two Open Farm and Open Industry days for EU citizens	>15	Scheduled for the 2 nd Reporting Period.

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	No. of participants	>2,000	Scheduled for the 2 nd Reporting Period.
Clustering activities	No. of liaison meetings with relevant EU funded projects from the Green Deal (H2020) and the Horizon Europe framework. MoUs signed with respective stakeholders along with minutes from meetings	>15	3 liaison meetings 0 MoUs signed
Engagement with stakeholders	No. of stakeholders engaged through the project's communication channels	>50,000	>90,000
	No. of stakeholders from the food industry comprising the valorisation board of Watson	>50	Scheduled for the 2 nd Reporting Period.
	No. of stakeholders registered for the demonstration events	>5,000	Scheduled for the 2 nd Reporting Period.
Videos	No. of videos published on Watson's YouTube channel	2	8
	No. of views	>1,000/video	754
TV mini-series	No. of mini-series episodes produced	3	Scheduled for the 2 nd Reporting Period.
Publications	No. of peer-reviewed papers/articles published in proceedings and online in premium quality conferences and journals	>15	1
	No. of other types of publications (e.g. press releases, magazine articles, media outlets, and online platforms)	>10	4
High-level materials for policymakers	No. of white papers for policy recommendations, published and disseminated through the project website and social media	3 (1/year)	Scheduled for the 2 nd Reporting Period.
	No. of sets of best practices with related statistics from different EU/EU associated countries uploaded on the Watson website	20	Scheduled for the 2 nd Reporting Period.

During the first half of the project (M1-M18), Watson partners have generally made positive progress in relation to the proposed KPIs. As shown in the table above, some activities require a noticeable increase in effort to reach the target values by the project's end. However, many of these activities (workshops for consumers and food safety authorities, training activities, stakeholders' engagement activities, TV mini-series, scientific publications, high-level materials for policymakers) correspond to the dissemination of the project results, thus the second half of the project (M18-M36) is key to enhance them, as most of the results are expected to be developed within this period.

On the other hand, in the first period, certain activities have already exceeded the proposed target value (e.g. the Watson website has already managed to exceed 3,000 unique visitors, a figure that was foreseen for 36 months, i.e., the whole duration of the project). Other indicators, such as the number of followers and publications on social networks, or the number of views of the first Watson video, also show positive figures, considering that the target values are relatively ambitious. Table 9 introduces some changes regarding the KPIs table included in both the deliverable D6.2 and the project proposal. Given that the communication and dissemination strategy is constantly being reviewed and improved, it has been considered appropriate to update this table to better reflect the type of key activities to be carried out and their expected scope. This means that some indicators that were not initially included in the original KPIs table have been added in this deliverable (e.g. "No. of roll-up banners", "No. of newsletters", "No. of training activities organised", "No. of liaison meetings", "No. of stakeholders engaged through the project's communication channels", among others).

5. Conclusion

This deliverable provides a report of the communication and dissemination activities carried out during the first half of the Watson project (M1-M18), as well as a practical overview of next steps to facilitate monitoring efforts. Thus, it establishes the framework for the consortium to support Watson's long-term success and impact by building on the current strategy and changing it as needed to reflect current conditions. It is important to note that this report represents the first phase of the communication and dissemination activities, which corresponds to months M1-M12 and the engagement of stakeholders from the food chain, consumer associations and scientific communities; as well as represents part of the second phase (M12-M30), i.e. the promotion through communication and dissemination activities of Watson's initial findings and results. Therefore, subsequent iterations will provide more detailed information on the upcoming phases, that is, phase 2 (currently underway) and phase 3, which corresponds to months M30-M36 and aims at the

adoption of the solutions and the preparation of exploitation plans for further deployment of Watson. The shift is expected to become more evident after the launch of some key deliverables and the commencement of pilot activities during the second half of the project, when it will be possible to provide more details on the solutions developed under Watson.

Since the communication and dissemination activities are planned to be carried out throughout the entire duration of the project, Watson is committed to regularly evaluating the effectiveness of the communication and dissemination efforts, using the predefined KPIs to measure its impact and make necessary adjustments for improved outcomes. Thus, all consortium members are actively involved in these tasks, promoting and sharing the results and progress of the project through the channels that best suit their organisations and audiences. In this sense, Watson will continue to enhance those communication and dissemination channels that show the best performance, i.e., the project website, Watson social networks and the participation in events; at the same time, partners expect to significantly increase their efforts to involve stakeholders (including policymakers), mainly through the organisation of events and training activities, and the Watson workshops to be held are key in this respect. Furthermore, the consortium remains optimistic that the dissemination effort will naturally increase as we deliver results, especially the scientific publications and the high-level materials for policymakers. Thus, partners will continue to work on “Task 6.1 - Dissemination, Communication and Watson Branding”, “Task 6.2 - Stakeholders’ Training, Community Engagement and Liaison with Other Initiatives”, and “Task 6.3 - Innovation Management, Market Analysis and Commercial Roadmap”; and will start working on “Task 6.4 - Standardization Activities and Policy Recommendations based on the Farm to Fork Strategy, SDG for Food and the Green Deal”.